

Nutritional Impact of Sprouted *Pennisetum glaucum*, Functional Ingredients on Covid-19

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Abstract:- Public health recommendations encourage the selection of a balanced diet to foster health and well-being through research in achieving good health and well being target 3 of sustainable development goals (SDGS). Since over two years that the pandemic was declared and the world struggle with corona virus diseases (Covid-19) pandemic, there is lack of clinically effective therapies, and attention is shifting to different ways in order to strengthen the immune system. Previous studies in assessment of plants properties for combating covid-19 were generally focused on fruits and vegetables functional ingredients. Recently from research, cereals are gaining importance as a health promoting nutritious crop. It was discovered that pearl millet grains have a high potential for therapeutic purpose because of their gluten free, highest in dietary fibre contents, essential amino acid contents, as well as essential minerals and vitamins. This research work was designed and conducted to determine the effect of processing (sprouting) on the mineral and vitamin contents of *Pennisetum glaucum*. Data were subjected to descriptive evaluation and computation. The results showed that there were enhancements in mineral and vitamin contents of *Pennisetum glaucum* after sprouting. Zn (42.90±0.08), Fe (48.20±0.06) and some other minerals have over 10% level of enhancement while vitamin B₉ (-21.0), vitamin C (-13.7) and other vitamins also experienced over 20% level of enhancement. This information about sprouted *Pennisetum glaucum* could be useful in the formulation and production of adult and infant food supplements in respect of minerals and vitamins to improve health, combat covid-19 and optimize cereal potential generally.

Keywords:- Nutritional Impact, Sprouted *Pennisetum Glaucum*, Functional Ingredients, Covid-19.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing rate of population coupled with high cost and dwindling availability of plant foods and animal feeds have resulted in malnourishment and ill health (Ogunlade et al; 2009). Malnourished people need to consume adequate calories for growth and maintenance in order to overcome the problem of economic crisis leading to under nutrition or Protein-Energy Malnutrition (PEM) (WHO, 2000). Availability of plant food which could serve

as cheap protein and energy sources, of which could be useful in the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which are good health (Goal 1), zero hunger (Goal 2) and no poverty (Goal 3). The quest to source for nutrient rich plant food that can adequately supply the nutrient needed and therapeutic purpose for adult and children calls for a continuous research into cereals (Ogunlade et al; 2011). Cereals belong to the family Poaceae or Gramineae which are monocotyledonous flowering plants known as grasses (Adeyeye, 1992). Millets have been important staples in the semi-arid tropic of Africa countries which are still the principal sources of energy, protein, vitamin and minerals for millions of the people in these regions (Yadare, 2016). Poaceae includes the cereal grasses, bamboos and the grasses of natural grassland and cultivated lawns and pasture (FAO, 2006). The nutritional, therapeutic and medicinal benefits of cereal (pearl millet) can be attributed to the presence of essential minerals and vitamins constituents in them. Enhancement through processing (sprouting) and characterization of essential minerals and vitamins from herbal product or medicinal plants (Pearl millet) have led to the discovery of recent distinguished pharmaceutical, health care products as well as preservatives (Ara, Buckhari, solaiman and Bakir, 2012).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The samples used for this research work were purchased from major markets located in Ado Ekiti and Ikere Ekiti. The bulk samples after sorting were divided into two sets: the first set was soaked in a clean plastic bowl with distilled water and covered with muslin bag and kept on the bench for five days allow sprouting to occur. The second set was air-dried and milled and kept in the refrigerator for further analysis. The sprouted samples were collected, drained of any water and then air-dried and milled. The milled samples were kept in the refrigerator for further analysis. Mineral and vitamins compositions were determined according to method described by Association of Official Analytical Chemists (A.O.A.C) (2005).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The highest level for the minerals in the samples were observed in sprouted *pennisetum glaucum* and recorded as follows: Co (0.93±0.20), Cr (32.50±0.10), Mn (18.90±0.00), Cu (6.26±0.06), Ca (46.80±0.66), Zn (42.90±0.08), Fe

(48.20±0.06), Na (-9.30±0.06), and K (2355.70±0.11) all in mg/100g. Table 1 showed the coefficient of variation for all the mineral elements it was revealed that the entire CV% of all the sample groups were very low as follows: UPG (0.002-7.83), and SPG (0.004-8.72). The value for Zn in sprouted pearl millet is a little bit higher (42mg/100g) and compare well with the tolerable upper intake level (40mg/day) as set by FAO/WHO (2019). The level of Cu in the unsprouted (0.94mg/100g) and sprouted (6.26mg/100g) were higher than the level of Cu (0.60,gg/100g) millet and compares well than that of maize in a research carried out by Adeyeye and Ajewole, 1992. In the unsprouted *pennisetum glaucum* flour, Co, Cr, Mn, Ca, Fe, Na and K were less concentrated than the sprouted one. There was an enhancement in the level of Co, Cr, Mn, Cu, Ca, Zn, Fe, Na and K by 1.5%, -190.70%, -18.90%, 563.6-%, -28.70%, -23.60%, -25.30%, -122.00% and -8.30% respectively. Level of mineral enhancement was found at the highest level in copper. They all follow the same trend. This work is in agreement with previous studies which reported that processing cereals depletes their mineral and tannin content (Gene and Haroid, 2004). The increase in the calcium content of the sprouted grain flour compared favourably with the result of a research study on sprouting characteristics and associated changes in nutritional composition of co-operating Chingakham, (2015). Also, the increase in calcium content of cowpea after sprouting may be attributed to presence of calcium salt in water used during sprouting process Dave et al; (2008) and Davies, (1979). All rxy were significant at r=0.05 and n-2 degree of freedom. The coefficient of alienation (C_A) ranged from 0.82-14.1%. The standard mineral safety index (MSI) for the minerals are Na (4.8), Mg (15), P(10), Ca (10), Fe (6.7), Zn (33) and Cu (33). Table 3 and 4 showed the mineral safety index of Na, Ca, Fe, Cu, and Zn for the unsprouted and sprouted flour sample *Pennisetum glaucum*. In all, the unsprouted and sprouted flour sample *Pennisetum glaucum*, Fe MSI values are -10.50 and 14.80 for UPG and SPG respectively. This value of Fe indicates that there is abnormally high level of Fe in all the samples. For the Zn mineral safety index values, differences between the MSI and the samples MSI with respective values of -43.30, and -61.40 for UPG, and SPG were observed respectively. Positive difference between the standard MSI and the sample MSI were observed for sodium, calcium, and Cu values in all the flour samples. This result indicates that the *Pennisetum glaucum* both unsprouted and sprouted samples

were okay in terms of calcium, sodium, and copper intake. Overloading of sodium in the body can even lead to secondary hypertension. Among the computed mineral ratios in Table 5, K/Na, Na/K, Ca/Na, Fe/Cu, Ca/K, Zn/Cu were all better in unsprouted *Pennisetum glaucum* than in the sprouted sample. This is an indication that both sprouted do not elevate any of these ratios. The levels (mg/100g) of vitamin A in this present report as shown on Table 6 and 7 were lower than those reported for raw and processed in a research carried out by Adesina (2015) similarly. The levels recorded in this present study for the raw and processed cereals flour samples were seriously lower than those reported for raw and processed red pepper (In et al; 2012). The levels in the samples were comparably lower than the recommended daily allowance (RDA). In any case, to meet up with the RDA foods rich in vitamin B₁ needs to be consumed alongside with the *pennisetum glaucum*. The present reports on the other hand were comparably higher than the levels reported for cosmos variety seeds (0.022-0.021mg/100g) and sassako variety seeds (0.016-0.017) both for raw and processed samples (Gwana et al., 2014). It was so evident that sprouting enhanced the levels of water soluble and fat soluble vitamins when compared the unsprouted whole flour sample of *pennisetum glaucum*. However, in the fat—soluble vitamin group, the highest level of enhancement was observed among the samples as follows; vitamin K (-10.1) while the least enhancement was found in vitamin E(-5.10). For *pennisetum glaucum* sample among the water-soluble vitamins, the highest enhancement was observed in B₉ (-21.0) while other enhanced vitamins were observed as B₅ (-11.8); B₁₂ (-140); B₃ (-13.6) and C (-13.7), B₆ (-0.7), B₁ (-1.0) and B₂ (-7.4). The least enhanced vitamins were vitamin K (-3.50) and E (-7.40). In table 1.7, the rx levels were positively high (0.99816-0.99992) whereas the Rxy ranged from 0.88164 to 0.94550 as the rxy were significant at r=0.05 and n-2 degree of freedom. The coefficient of alienation (CA) ranged from 0.01-0.06% whereas the corresponding index of forecasting efficiency (IFE) ranged from 94.4 to 98.7%. In this research work, all the water- soluble vitamins were enhanced at various degrees and percentage by sprouting while in all the fat soluble vitamins for all the samples, there were enhancements. In this research work, eight antinutritional factors (ANFs) were detected namely: Tannin, Saponnin, Flavonoids, Phenolies, Alkanoids, Gycosides, Oxalate and phytate.

Table 1 The Coefficient of Variation for all the Mineral Elements

S/N		UPG/SPG MEAN±SD	CV%
1.	Co	0.93±0.08	8.20
2.	Cr	21.86±0.08	0.46
3.	Mn	17.38±0.08	0.45
4.	Cu	3.6±0.05	2.36
5.	Ca	41.61±0.43	0.98
6.	Zn	38.82±0.44	0.22
7.	Fe	43.32±0.09	0.22
8.	Na	21.23±0.07	0.37
9.	K	2265.94±0.08	0.003

Table 2 Represents Statistical Analysis of Mineral Composition (Linear Correlation and Regression Data from Table 1)

	Correlation (rxy)	Coefficient of determination rxy ²	Regression (Rxy)	Coefficient of Alienation (Ca)	Index of forecasting efficiency (IFE)	Critical Table vale (TV)	Remark
UPG/SPG	0.99999	0.99999	0.92677	0.82	98.2	0.4680	S

Table 3 represents Mineral Safety Index

Fe			Na			Ca			Zn			Cu			
TV	CV	D	TV	CV	D	TV	CV	D	TV	CV	D	TV	CV	D	
6.7	17.2	-10.5	4.8	1.27	3.53	10	0.30	9.70	33	76.3	-43.3	33	1.40	31.6	UPG
6.7	21.5	-14.8	4.8	0.28	4.52	10	0.39	9.61	33	94.4	-61.4	33	9.40	23.6	SPG

Table 4 represents Mineral Safety Index

Fe			Na			Ca			Zn			Cu			
MEA	SD	CV %	MEA	SD	CV %	MEA	SD	CV %	MEA	SD	CV %	MEA	SD	CV %	
11.47	4.34	37	3.21	1.46	45	5.60	4.63	92.68	20.73	14.97	29.45	22.07	14.62	56.24	UPG
14.30	6.05	42	3.20	2.06	64	6.67	4.45	36.37	50.87	18.50	36.37	22.00	9.70	44.09	SPG

Table 5 represents Quality Parameter and Ratio in Mineral Composition of *Pennisetum glaucum* (sprouted and unsprouted).

	UPG/SPG	
	MEAN±SD	CV%
Co	0.5±3.81	4.85
Cr	16.50±0.33	16.43
MN	9.44±0.39	9.65
CU	3.15±1.42	3.64
CA	23.52±0.66	23.74
N	14.33±0.31	21.56
Fe	24.16±0.25	24.14
Na	14.69±0.16	14.77
K	1177.93±0.07	177.88
K/Na	41.14±1.05	40.19
Na/K	0.27±14.47	19.52
Ca/Na	2.24±1.71	4.17
Fe/Cu	5.64±0.55	3.89
Ca/K	0.775.64±0.5514.19	132.39
Zn/Cu	4.725.64±0.550.72	3.55

Table 6 represents Vitamins Composition of *Pennisetum glaucum* (sprouted and unsprouted).

S/N	NAME	UPG			SPG		
		MEAN	±SD	CV%	MEAN	±SD	CV%
1	Vitamin B3	4.16	±0.14336	3.444877	4.72	±0.103685	2.19349335
2	Vitamin B6	0.76	±0.01099	1.446273	0.75	±0.016215	2.14785742
3	Vitamin c	4.75E-05	±1.8E-06	3.835603	5.40E-05	±1.15E-06	2.11901901953
4	Vitamin A	2.35E-06	±2.6E-07	11.12812	2.80E-06	±1.31E-07	4.6568996
5	Vitamin B1	0.27	±0.01436	5.278039	0.27	±0.007358	2.67679546
6	Vitamin B2	0.05	±0.00187	3.742744	0.05	±0.001834	3.41445145
7	Vitamin D	7.92E-06	±7E-08	0.886579	8.90E-06	±1.29E-07	1.46137722
8	Vitamin E	1.54	±0.12017	7.781329	1.65	±0.107253	6.46706635
9	Vitamin B9	0.004	±0.00026	5.719452	0.005	±0.000155	2.82541539
10	Vitamin K	5.70E-06	±5.3E-07	9.387849	5.90E-06	±1.38E-07	2.3510424
11	Vitamin B5	1.23	±0.08788	7.114714	1.38	±0.19004	13.7597129
12	Vitamin B12	1.14E-05	±1.1E-06	9.765681	1.30E-05	±1.63E-06	12.6261896

Table 7 represents Vitamins Composition of *Pennisetum glaucum* (sprouted and unsprouted).

S/N	NAME	UPG/SPG	
		MEAN±SD	CV%
1	Vitamin B3	4.44±0.12	2.81
2	Vitamin B6	0.76±0.01	1.80
3	Vitamin C	5.08±1.48	2.98
4	Vitamin A	2.58±1.95	7.89
5	Vitamin B1	0.27±0.01	3.97
6	Vitamin B2	0.05±0.00	3.57
7	Vitamin D	8.41±4.15	1.17
8	Vitamin E	1.59±0.10	7.12
9	Vitamin B9	0.0003±0.00	4.27
10	Vitamin K	5.80±3.34	5.87
11	Vitamin B5	1.31±0.14	10.44
12	Vitamin B12	1.22±1.37	11.17

Table 8 represents summary of the vitamin composition of *Pennisetum glaucum* (sprouted and unsprouted).

Vitamins	UPG-SPG (%)	MEAN±SD	CV%
Vitamin B3	-0.6(-13.6%)	0.4± 0.23	54.5
Vitamin B6	0.005(0.70%)	0.31±0.25	79.65
Vitamin C	-0.000007(-13.7%)	0.000015±0.0362	0.01
Vitamin A	-0.0000005(-19.1%)	0.0000058±0.0103	0.02
Vitamin B1	-0.003(-1.00%)	0.040.31±0.043	107.5
Vitamin B2	-0.004(-7.40%)	0.00530.31±0.00000675	0.04
Vitamin D	-0.000001(-12.4%)	0.0000230.31±0.05	0.02
Vitamin E	-0.1(-7.40%)	0.12±0.105	87.5
Vitamin B9	-0.001(-21.4%)	0.0011±0.011	1.00
Vitamin K	-0.0000002(-3.5%)	0.000000016±0.00000102	0.02
Vitamin B5	-0.1(-11.8%)	0.0975±0.000076	0.02
Vitamin B ₁₂	-0.000002(-14.0%)	0.000055±0.0000000073	0.01

Table 9 represents statistical analysis (linear correlation and regression) of data from table 6.

Groups	Correl (rxy)	Determ.(Rxy ²)	Regress (Rxy)	CA	IFE	Critical table value (TV)	Remark
UPG/SPG	0.99961	0.99922	0.88399	2.77	97.2	0.5341	S

IV. CONCLUSION

In this research work all the minerals, water soluble and fat soluble vitamins were enhanced at various degrees and percentages by sprouting of which the level in this report compared well with the recommended daily allowance of 3.0mg/day for individual of 7 years old and above (NRC 1989 and USDA 1987) which could also be useful in the treatment of covid-19 and other related diseases.

REFERENCES

[1]. Adeyeye A.; Ajewole K. (1992). Chemical composition and fatty acid profiles of cereals in Nigeria. Food chem. 44:41-44.
 [2]. Agrawal A.J.; (1992). Processing of pearl millet for its more effective utilization. Ph.D thesis, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana, India, 183pp.
 [3]. Achana (2002). Development and nutritional evaluation of pearl millet based diabetic food. Ph.D thesis, CCS Haryana Agricultural University Hisar, Haryana, India. 176pp.

[4]. Bello F.A.; Enidiork S.E.; Azubuine B.C.; (2017). Effect of stepping and sprouting on the nutritional, anti-nutritional and functional properties of pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) starch. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 4, issue 9.
 [5]. F.A.O (2006). Official Agricultural statistics 18th edition, Food and Agricultural Organization, Canada pg 1002-1004.
 [6]. Ogunlade, I. and Falana, C.O. (2009). Effects of Traditional processing on the Amino acid profile of Bitter yam (*Discorea dumentararoum*). International Journal of Chemical Science.
 [7]. Riahhanatu M.B.; Modu, S.; Falmata, A.S.; Shettima, Y.A. AND Heman M. (2011). Effect of processing (Sprouting and fermentation) of five local varieties of sorghum on some biochemical parameters. Biokemistri 23(2): 91-96.
 [8]. Serna-saldiwar, S.; and Rooney, I.W. (1996). Structure and chemistry of sorghum and millets. In sorghum and millets: chemistry and technology. Dendy, D.A.V (ed). A.A.C.C, usa.

- [9]. WHO (2000). World Health Organization, Department of Nutrition for Health and Development. Nutrition for health and development: a global agenda for combating malnutrition. World Health Organization.
- [10]. Wilson, D.L. and Harrison, R.G. (1991). Predicting the solubility of recombinant proteins in *E.coli* Biotechnology, 9:443-448.
- [11]. Adesina, A.J. (2015). Effects of processing methods on the chemical composition and functional properties of Africana breadfruit (*treculia africana*) seeds flour. Ph.D Thesis.
- [12]. A.O.A.C. (2005): Official Methods of Analysis 18th ed., AOAC International, Maryland, U.S.A.
- [13]. Bello, F.A., Enidiok, S.E., Azubunie, B.C. (2017). Effect of stepping and sprouting on the nutritional, anti-nutritional and functional properties of pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) starch. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 4, issue 9.
- [14]. Gwana, A.B., Bako, M.M., Bagudu, B.Y., Sadiq, A.B. AND Abdullahi, M.M (2014). Determinations J of phytochemicals, vitamins, minerals and proximate compositions of varieties of watermelon seeds cultivated in Borno State, North –Eastern Nigeria. International Journal of Nutrition and Food Science, 3(4): 238-245.